

From Digital Gaps to Seamless Journeys: Insights into the Erasmus+ Traineeship Experience

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About DETAS

DETAS (Digitalising Erasmus Traineeship Application Support) is an innovative project designed to enhance the Erasmus+ traineeship experience for students, universities, and host organisations. It seeks to address the growing demand for high-quality traineeships across Europe by upgrading and digitalising the Erasmus+ Intern portal. The project aligns with key EU policies such as the European Strategy for Universities, the Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027), and the European Year of Skills, with a focus on digital transformation and employability.

By improving the Erasmus+ Intern portal, DETAS aims to increase the number of Erasmus+ traineeships, which currently supports around 75,000 participants, with the goal of reaching 100,000 annually. The project focuses on providing students with better access to resources, supporting their journey from pre-departure to on-site traineeships, and streamlining the recruitment process for companies. DETAS will implement a series of capacity-building activities, policy recommendations, and technical innovations to ensure that the portal remains a vital tool for connecting students and companies across Europe.

DETAS will also address challenges faced by Erasmus+ trainees, such as local integration, pre-departure support, and on-site assistance, ensuring that the experience benefits both students and host organisations. Through collaboration with key partners, the project will create a more efficient and accessible platform that supports youth employability and digital skills development across Europe.

The DETAS project spans three years, from January 2024 to December 2026, structured into distinct phases to ensure a comprehensive approach to improving Erasmus+ traineeships. The first year focuses on needs analysis, research, and the development of a technical blueprint, which includes desk research and surveys to assess key areas for innovation. In 2025, the project will transition into implementing innovations on ErasmusIntern.org, alongside developing traineeship quality labels and improved guidelines for universities. The final year will see the technical release of the enhanced platform, advocacy efforts, and policy recommendations based on the project's findings.

PART 1

Literature Review

1.1 Backdrop

The global landscape is changing rapidly. Developments in communications, transportation, supply chain, connectivity, and technology are 'shrinking the world'. Models of working are increasingly global, featuring globally dispersed teams on shared projects, co-located multi-cultural teams on a single site, temporary secondments, and the 'follow-the-sun' model (Twomey & Cvitan, 2017). Such models mean that interacting with people from different cultural backgrounds have become a norm of working life in many countries and regions, as well as an aspect of life more generally. In this increasingly globally interconnected, interdependent and urbanised world, employers recognise the need for graduates who possess an international orientation and an ability to operate in culturally diverse contexts (Illie, 2019; Ogden and Van Mol, 2020; Tushar and Sooraksa, 2023; Xiaochi, 2012).

At the same time, higher education institutions (HEIs) are seeking ways to respond to this new paradigm, often by incorporating global or international dimensions into their curricula and activities (Crossman and Clarke, 2010; Reinhard & Satow, 2007). Such learning is also evident in graduate attribute statements which reference, e.g., global citizenship, international knowledge, and competence in culturally diverse environments (Schech et al., 2017). This backdrop has spawned increased interest and activity in the domain of international work placement (McRae et al., 2016; Reinhard & Gerloff, 2020). At EU level, it is contended that the Erasmus+ programme has been instrumental in the growth of international work placements over the last two decades (Dunlap & Mapp, 2017).

In this context, the Osnabruck Declaration (2020) draws attention to the importance of supporting students in the switching of their sites of learning from one country to a different country. However, it remains the case that study abroad is overwhelmingly the primary conduit of international mobility for students, with traineeships accounting for less than 30% of Erasmus+ learning mobility (European Commission, 2023). The literature regularly points to a dearth of research on international work placement (Andresen et al., 2022; Cranston et al., 2020; Kattiyapornpoing & Almeida, 2021) and the dominance of study abroad in the scholarly mobility literature (Dunlap & Mapp, 2017). It is of note that this literature review suggests that the overwhelming majority of published literature on work placement emanates from the North American and Australasian regions, with an evident paucity of research undertaken in the European context.

¹ A business model used by companies to provide support to customers regardless of location or time zone.

1.2 Terminology

The literature review reveals a plethora of terminology regarding work placement. The terms traineeship, practicum, internship, placement, work placement, stage, intra, professional practice, work-integrated learning, cooperative education, work-based learning and experiential learning are all used in the discourse, often interchangeably (Twomey, 2019).

Work placements are also analysed across a number of dimensions. Maertz, Stoebel and Marks' (Maertz, Stoebel and Marks, 2014) framework examines placements from the perspectives of, e.g., paid vs. unpaid; accredited vs. uncredited; high levels of formal learning objectives vs. low or none; implied opportunity for future full time graduate employment vs. no implication of the same.

For the purposes of this desk research, an Erasmus+ traineeship can be understood to mean a period of institutionally sanctioned, in-company work experience undertaken by a student (or new graduate) outside of their home country, for the purposes of intentional learning, in the context of the Erasmus+ mobility programme.

1.3 Benefits to trainees

Work placements represent a shift from passive pedagogy to active learning, in effect giving life to theory (Billet, 2011; Essl et al., 2020). The literature review lends significant support to the view that this form of learning adds value to students' academic studies. Cited benefits to students include opportunities to undertake active, real-world learning in an authentic workplace setting; put into practice their classroom learnings in a workplace setting; develop their skills; develop a sense of their own abilities; enhance their understanding of their own learning; and gain a positional advantage in the graduate labour market (Brooks & Youngson, 2016; Coll, 2004; Tomlinson, 2017).

Across the literature, a range of benefits specific to international work placement are identified. They include enhanced employability, the development of transferable skills, the ability to think outside the box, increased confidence, adaptability, flexibility, appreciation of difference, development of innovative practices, and greater understanding of global interdependence (Barker, Kinsella and Bossers, 2010; Brassier-Rodrigues & Kluge, 2023; Gilin and Young 2009; Kattiyapornpong & Almeida, 2021; Jones, 2013). For employers, on the other hand, placements allow them to: draw on an immediate source of inexpensive, temporary and flexible talent; bring in fresh enthusiasm and innovation to the organisation; gain access to early career graduate talent; and enhance university-industry partnerships (Reinhard et al., 2007; Tanaka, 2009; Twomey, 2019).

International learning mobility (study and work) supports students in acquiring new knowledge, in learning from different sources, and in testing existing assumptions and skills in new situations, in a second country (Flander and Korada, 2020). It is suggested that the benefits of work placements are amplified when undertaken in an international context (Berry, 2007). This may be explained by the perceived intensity of the international experience and the requirement for students to manage themselves on an unaccompanied work placement (Simpson et al., 2016).

The benefit of international work placement is that it appears to prepare students to be globally ready (McRae et al., 2016). In this context, international work placements have been found to enhance globalised social, cultural and human capital and increase students' confidence when entering the global labour market (Kattiyapornpong & Almeida, 2021).

This is consistent with research by Gribble et al. (2014) which reported that international placements have the effect of enhancing key personal, professional, and cultural competencies. In this context, the Erasmus Impact Study (Brandenburg et al., 2014) reported that 99% of HEIs observed a significant increase in students' confidence and adaptability on their return from international work placement or Erasmus study abroad period.

Wong and Coll's (2001) study focused on students' perceptions of international placement. It found that students associate international placement with career success and enhancement of both practical and personal skills. This is evidentially supported by a finding that one third of students who undertook an Erasmus traineeship received a job offer from their host organisation (Brandenburg et al., 2014). A study of student perceptions by Behrisch (2016) found that, on completion of an international work placement, the majority of respondents rated their experience as having much or extreme value to their future career prospects. The literature also suggests that international internships help students to accelerate their career adaptability, career readiness, and preparation (Kattiyapornpong & Almeida, 2021). In their research covering 30 countries, Andresen et al. (2022) examined the link between international work placement and career success, finding that employees who have undertaken international work placements have consistently higher career success returns than those who had not.

It is suggested that young adults who have taken the challenge of moving abroad reflect a specific personality profile that is appreciated by employers (Van Moll, 2017). Supporting this, King and Shondhi (2018) found that students who undertake international work placements are more likely to be perceived as confident and adventurous by employers. This is in line with Cranston's (2020) view that international placement has a symbolic value that conveys to employers a proven ability to work in different cultural contexts.

Certainly, it has been found that employers can perceive graduates with international experience as being better able to build relationships and conduct global business, citing these graduates' ability to understand and appreciate sensitivities around culture, language, and law and their influence on business practice (Crossman and Clarke, 2010). Some studies suggest that knowledge of a foreign language is seen by employers as an attractive additional skill as opposed to being an essential requirement for global careers (Eaton, Kleshinski & Andrew, 2014; Twomey & Cvitan, 2017). Explanatory power for this may lie in the fact that English has become the lingua franca for global business in many countries (Jackson, 2010).

Much of the scholarly discourse around international placement generally and associated benefits more specifically is - not surprisingly - centred around the overarching theme of intercultural competence. Key manifestations of intercultural competencies include cross-cultural communication, dealing with uncertainty, fostering curiosity, international-mindedness, resilience, adaptability, and empathy (Cvitan et al., 2024; Deardorff, D. K., & Arasaratnam-Smith, 2017; Salter et al., 2021).

Cultural competencies are not easily defined or accessed and cannot be learned in a traditional lecture theatre (Gribble et al., 2017; Peterson et al., 2017). Rather, they can be developed through direct experiences of encounters with difference; international work experience is a salient example of this (Auld & Morris, 2019; Cranston et al., 2022).

Differences between the impacts of study abroad and international work placements emerged across the discourse, with students perceiving the impact of their work placement to be significantly greater across the cognitive, interpersonal, intrapersonal domains (Flander & Korada, 2020). In her sample of Japanese students, Kirchhoff (Kirchhoff, 2015) compared a group of students who had undertaken study abroad-only with those who had undertaken both study and placement abroad. In comparison to the 'study-only' group, the 'study + placement' cohort reported higher levels of English language skills development.

They also reported higher levels of self-directed action, acceptance of responsibility, and openness to challenges. Similarly, in the graduate recruitment and selection process, employers appear to assign higher value to international work placement than to study abroad experience, with international work placements perceived as being more challenging than study abroad

1.4 Benefits to employers

The literature stresses the challenges cited by employers in identifying, attracting, recruiting, and retaining graduate talent (Brown et al., 2018). Employers typically seek graduate applicants who can demonstrate work readiness and the skills and capabilities required to thrive in the graduate workplace (Jackson et al., 2017). In this context, work placement occupies a specific place, as it combines a foretaste of the world of work and contributes significantly to students' work readiness. It is regularly presented in the literature as a mechanism for delivering 'plug-in-and-play' (Brown et al., 2001) graduates who can hit the ground running.

Aligned with this, the discourse highlights the limitations of traditional recruitment and selection instruments such as CVs, interviews, and educational qualifications (Bach & Edwards, 2012; Highhouse, 2008) and, in particular, their waning power to predict the skills, role, and organisation-fit of applicants (Twomey, 2019). In this context, the advantage of work placements is that they offer employers the opportunity to observe in an authentic work setting, over an extended period of time, student intern' 'capabilities and performance (Rose et al., 2021; Elarde & Chong, 2012). In effect, it provides employers with the opportunity to realistically assess students' talents and fit, before making a significant offer of a graduate role, and without the complication of a long-term commitment (Drewery, 2020; Hamburg et al., 2013; Rose et al., 2014). This is supported by work by Melink et al., (2014) that found that internships are regarded as a central recruiting mechanism by three out of four large companies and approximately half of SMEs.

Work placements offer employers the opportunity to build their on-campus brand with students, at an early stage in their studies. Employers can use this 'high touch' conduit as a way to advertise their graduate opportunities and to develop a long-term talent pipeline (Hurst et al., 2012). They can achieve this by maximising their attractiveness to student interns and by motivating and nurturing them, with a view to converting them into future graduate recruits (Twomey, 2019). A recent survey of graduate employers (National Association of College Employers, 2024) showed that 53% of eligible student interns (trainees) are converted into full time graduate hires. Reflecting this, Sattler and Peters (Sattler and Peters, 2012) found that employers have a preference for hiring graduates who have undertaken a work placement in their organisation.

Leveraged in this way, work placement confers a significant competitive edge on employers in what can be a very contested graduate recruitment market. It has also been shown that recruitment, onboarding and training costs are reduced where organisations employ interns for graduate roles (Holyoak, 2013). Furthermore, there is evidence that previous student interns who take up graduate roles in the same organisation hold positions of higher responsibility and enjoy more rapid career advancement compared to other employees (Gohringer, 2002, Maertz et al., 2014).

Taking on students on work placement can alleviate employees' workload, particularly during busy periods, often in a cost-effective way (Ismail, 2018). The discourse also suggests that work placements add value to workplace culture (Fleming et al., 2023). For many employers, students' enthusiasm and vitality create a different dynamic in the workplace (Fleming & Pretty, 2019). Specifically, students can influence the workplace and team by providing fresh perspectives, challenging existing ways of doing things, and sharing creative and technological insights (EURES, 2022; Wang et al., 2018; Mgya & Mbekomize, 2014). Supervising a student intern can also create mentoring and management development opportunities (Ferns et al., 2021), allowing staff to build their skills profile. Interestingly, it is posited that organisations that host international student interns accrue benefits including exposure to diverse cultural nuances and norms, and the development of a more collegial and compassionate workplace (Ferns et al., 2019).

1.5 Motivation of trainees

Given the well-documented array of its potential benefits, it might be intuited that students would be very motivated to undertake such an experience. Cranston et al. (2020) contend that there are multiple and complex motivations for undertaking international work placement. For some students, their motivation centres on engagement in ventures that they perceive may increase their employability.

They may pursue scarce international work placements as a mode of distinction that might confer a credential advantage on them in the graduate labour market (Cranston et al., 2020). This is in line with an employer's view that students who undertake international work experience convey confidence, self-reliance, and a sense of adventure (King and Shondhi, 2018; Van Moll, 2017). Alternatively, students' motivation may be simply the opportunity to move out of their comfort zone and pursue self-discovery. Behrisch (2016) found that the desire for novelty and the opportunity to meet new people act as important motivators.

The level of students' motivation and receptivity to undertaking international work placement has been examined, with the finding that higher levels of receptivity in individual students are related to higher levels of receptivity to international careers during their early career phase (Tharenou, 2003).

1.6 Challenges & constraints

Almost by definition, international work placements disrupt students' comfort zones, test their existing frames of understanding, and involve a reaction to a different place (Prazeres, 2017). These are what Mezirow refers to as disorienting dilemmas (Mezirow, 1991). Students not only have to undergo the sometimes-turbulent boundary passage from academia to an authentic workplace setting and an identity switch from student to their early professional selves, but they must often navigate a different culture, language, and lifestyle on international placement (Reinhard & Satow, 2007).

Recent discourse draws specific attention to a range of other challenges including financial resources and costs, fear of separation from family and friendship groups, lack of language skills, and security (Penneforte, 2024). This chimes with earlier research by Coll and Chapman (2000) who found that homesickness and loneliness during placement are significant issues for many students. In an exploration of student decision-making around international mobility, risk tolerance and uncertainty about the benefits of mobility programmes emerged as strong themes (Behrisch, 2016). Interestingly, the same study found that students who completed international placements were the student group with the highest risk tolerance.

It also identified risk categories, including health and safety and fear of the unknown. Students report cultural, political, communication, supervision, and personal problems during international placement (Niemantsverdiet et al., 2004). They also reference frustrations around information overload and the challenge of executing the boundary crossing from academia to work (Simpson et al., 2016). Finally, Pennaforte (2024) draws attention to students' low awareness of international work placement opportunities.

From the employers' perspective, on the other hand, cited challenges include managing additional paperwork for international interns and dealing with students' homesickness (Coll, 2004). From the universities' viewpoint, securing international work placements can be a complex and resource-intensive activity (Coll & Chapman, 2000). There are significant resource challenges, financial, manpower and logistical, in the deployment of a highly supported international placement model and not all higher education programmes have the capacity to offer such opportunities (Maynes et al., 2013). Crucially, Edwards et al. (2015) contend that, where there is a resistance to the concept of work placement generally within a university, this acts as a substantial inhibiting factor.

They further posit that commitment by a small number of academics is not a sustainable way to expand work placement activities.

The issue of privilege also arises in the literature, with questions raised about which students are able to access international placement opportunities (Beech, 2015; Forsberg, 2017). Research by Kattiyapornpong & Almeida (2021) examined students' pre-internship capital (viz., prior exposure to international travel, financial and family resources) and found that students with higher levels of pre-internship capital are more likely to take advantage of international internship opportunities.

So, even though international experience is often framed as an aspiration for all, if some students cannot access it, it could in fact perpetuate inequalities – albeit unwittingly (Cranston, 2022). This raises interesting questions for practitioners and universities. That said, Gates (2014) contends that there is much that can be done at the European level to support students in securing placements and that, in doing so, students will extract the maximum benefit for their own education and forge a pathway to meaningful and productive careers.

1.7 Preparation

There is an obligation on HEIs to adequately prepare students for international work placement. The literature strongly indicates that purposeful, adequate, and effective preparation is a key factor of success in international work placement (Peterson et al., 2017; Pennaforte, 2024). However, it should not be assumed that such appropriate preparation is universally deployed. For example, Brandenburg et al. (2014) found that only 51% of HEIs have implemented preparatory programmes for study or international work periods. Similarly, a survey by ESN (Escriva, 2015) reported that 45% of students undertaking a period of international work or study abroad received no preparation at all for their stay abroad. Where preparatory programmes are deployed, there is wide variation in models used. Dunlap and Mapp (2017) highlight the following differentiating aspects of preparatory programmes: formal vs. informal, assessed vs. unassessed, credit-bearing vs. unaccredited, compulsory vs. optional, pre-departure assignments/presentations vs. none, individual vs. larger group delivery, weekend/week/semester durations. Preparatory programmes generally tend to have a specific focus on equipping students with the resilience to cope with the challenging demands and tensions associated with making the boundary transition from the classroom to the workplace (Coll and Chapman, 2000).

However, preparatory programmes can include additional dimensions, including logistical and risk management aspects of international travel, stress management, self-care, and motivation (Hollis, 2012; Ramji et al., 2021; Salter et al., 2021). Schech et al. (2017) present a model of in-person real international business simulations that can act as an alternative to international work placement, or as an effective preparatory model for future international work experience. Screening of students for their suitability for international experience also receives attention in the discourse (Bain & Yaklin, 2019).

Not surprisingly, theories of intercultural development and cross-cultural competence emerge as important strands of preparation, with students encouraged to engage in critical reflection on themselves and their cultural values in order to increase their self-awareness and reduce their culture shock (Dunlap and Mapp, 2017; McRae et al., 2016). This is consistent with Engstrom & Jones' (2007) finding that cultural preparation is key to effective preparation for international placement. Gates (2014) highlights the importance of students articulating their learning goals prior to experience and then reflecting on those goals at the conclusion as it provides meaningful information for both the student and the university.

Aligned with this, students need to develop a clear set of expectations in order to optimise successful placement outcomes. This resonates with the work of Salter et al. (2021) which points to the importance of supporting students' readiness for potential expectation dissonance. They also call for the mobilisation of student agency to negotiate the sensemaking associated with such international learning.

The preparation of the employer also receives attention. Peterson et al. (2017) contend that careful planning should be undertaken to ensure that the host employer and supervisor are clear regarding the scope and knowledge of the student. This process should be facilitated in order to avoid a disconnect between expectations and realities during placement for both stakeholders. Edwards et al. (2015) suggest clear induction processes at the beginning of the placement and facilitated opportunities for reflection on placement experience at placement completion – for both the student and employers.

Gribble et al. (2014) highlight the fact that, notwithstanding cultural preparation, students report being overwhelmed by differences in work practice. They suggest that supervisors need to be aware of the impact of a new environment on students who are essentially professional neophytes operating in another cultural context.

1.8 Conclusion and next steps

The literature review points to the rise in international work placement activities and the rich range of benefits associated with it from the perspectives of all key stakeholders. It also reveals the many challenges involved in this switching of the site of learning from the classroom in one country to the workplace in another. These challenges may explain the relatively low numbers of students opting for this mobility channel in comparison with student participation in learning mobility.

To address some of these challenges, careful consideration should be given to how international work placement opportunities can be more effectively signposted to students and universities. A key factor of success in international work placements is overt institutional support for practitioners and academics. In this context, Erasmus+ traineeship mobility should be promoted more vigorously to the leadership of European HEIs as a discrete pillar of mobility, distinctive from learning mobility. Moreover, the non-elitist philosophy of the Erasmus+ traineeship mobility programmes should be showcased widely to higher education and employer partners.

There should be a specific focus on effective preparation of both students and employers, including comprehensive preparatory programmes, clear induction processes, and facilitated post-placement reflection for all stakeholders. This will support students in the negotiation of dissonance and in developing a comfort with the unknown. It will also provide clarity around the roles and expectations of all stakeholders, thus mitigating the risk of unmet expectations. Although explicit reference is not made to quality frameworks in international work placements, the theme of quality underscores much of the discourse. A starting point for the development of a quality Erasmus+ work placement programme might be the recently published Global Quality Work-Integrated-Learning Framework (WACE, 2024).

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PART 2

Policy and Initiatives

2.1 Context and development of Erasmus+ Traineeships

The Erasmus+ programme (European Commission, Erasmus+ Programme Guide, 2023), named after the Dutch philosopher Desiderius Erasmus of Rotterdam, is the cornerstone of European educational policy. Launched in 1987, the Erasmus Programme originally focused on student exchange, aiming to foster greater cross-cultural understanding and collaboration among European students. Over the years, the programme expanded its scope, reflecting the evolving needs of the European education and labour markets.

In 2007, the Erasmus Programme was integrated into the broader Erasmus+ initiative, which encompassed not only student exchanges but also traineeships, teaching assignments, and staff training, supporting more sectors than just higher education as it did initially. This integration marked a significant development, recognising the growing importance of practical, work-based learning experiences in addition to traditional academic studies.

Erasmus+ Traineeships were introduced in 2014 as part of the wider Erasmus+ programme to bridge the gap between theoretical education and practical work experience, providing students with opportunities to apply their academic knowledge in real-world settings. These traineeships aimed to enhance employability, foster entrepreneurial skills, and promote linguistic and cultural diversity. They were designed to benefit not only the students but also the host organisations by bringing in fresh perspectives and innovative ideas.

The inclusion of traineeships within the Erasmus+ framework responded to the increasing demand for highly skilled and adaptable graduates capable of navigating a dynamic and competitive job market. By 2014, Erasmus+ had significantly broadened its reach, offering traineeship opportunities to students at all levels of higher education, including those in vocational education and training (VET) programmes.

The evolution of Erasmus+ Traineeships reflects a strategic commitment to preparing Europe's youth for the challenges of a globalised economy. The European Institutions has continually adapted and expanded the programme to ensure that it meets the changing needs of both students and employers. Today, Erasmus+ supports over 1 million participants annually, with a significant portion engaging in traineeships across diverse sectors and industries (European Commission, 2016).

2.2 Policy and Educational Frameworks

The Erasmus+ Programme operates within a comprehensive policy and educational framework designed to enhance the quality and accessibility of education and training across Europe. This framework is underpinned by several key policies and initiatives that guide the implementation and development of Erasmus+ Traineeships.

2.2.1 Policy framework

For the Higher Education sector, at the heart of the policy framework is the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE), which provides the general quality framework for European and international cooperation activities that higher education institutions may carry out within Erasmus+ and currently includes more than 5000 Higher Education Institutions (European Commission, 2024). The ECHE outlines the fundamental principles and minimum requirements that institutions must adhere to, ensuring that all Erasmus+ activities, including traineeships, meet high standards of quality and fairness.

In addition to the ECHE, the European Commission has introduced the European Strategy for Universities, which aims to increase the annual participation in Erasmus+ traineeships to 100,000 students and fresh graduates annually by 2025. This strategy highlights the importance of mobility and international experience in enhancing the employability and skills of European students. It also stresses the need for stronger links between higher education institutions and the labour market, which Erasmus+ Traineeships are ideally positioned to support (European Commission, 2023).

The Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027) is another critical policy that influences the Erasmus+ Programme. This plan aims to support the digital transformation of education systems across Europe by fostering the development and adoption of innovative digital tools and methodologies. Within the context of Erasmus+ Traineeships, this policy encourages the integration of digital skills training and the use of digital platforms to facilitate remote and virtual traineeships, thus broadening access and participation (European Commission, Digital Education Action Plan, 2021).

The 2014 Council Recommendation on a Quality Framework for Traineeships (QFT) (Council of the EU, 2014/C 88/01, 2014) serves as a crucial benchmark for defining what

constitutes a high-quality traineeship. This recommendation establishes comprehensive undertaken outside formal education curricula and mandatory professional training. By setting these standards, the QFT aims to ensure that traineeships provide meaningful learning experiences, protect the rights of trainees, and foster fair and equitable working conditions. This framework has significantly influenced subsequent policies, including the proposal for a reinforced quality framework for traineeship introduced in recent years.

2.2.2 Educational frameworks

The educational framework for Erasmus+ Traineeships is deeply rooted in the principles of lifelong learning and student-centred education. The Bologna Process, which seeks to create a European Higher Education Area (EHEA), plays a pivotal role in shaping the educational strategies of the Erasmus+ Programme for this sector. By promoting the comparability of qualifications and encouraging the adoption of the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS), the Bologna Process facilitates the recognition of traineeship experiences across different countries and institutions.

“While affirming our support to the general principles laid down in the Sorbonne declaration, we engage in co-ordinating our policies to reach in the short term, and in any case within the first decade of the third millennium, the following objectives, which we consider to be of primary relevance in order to establish the European area of higher education and to promote the European system of higher education world-wide.” (European Ministers of Education Bologna Declaration, 1999).

Furthermore, the Learning Outcomes approach, central to the Bologna Process, is integral to the design and implementation of Erasmus+ Traineeships. This approach ensures that the knowledge, skills, and attitudes acquired during a traineeship are clearly defined, assessed, and recognised, both academically and professionally. It aligns traineeships with the broader educational objectives of higher education institutions, enhancing their relevance and impact (Council of the EU, 2021).

Quality assurance mechanisms are also a crucial component of the educational framework. The European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education - EQAR (<https://www.eqar.eu/>) and the European Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance - ESG (ENQA et. al., 2015) provide a robust quality assurance system that monitors and evaluates the implementation of Erasmus+ Traineeships. These mechanisms ensure that traineeships provide meaningful and high-quality learning experiences that contribute to the personal and professional development of students.

2.3 Current policy developments relevant to traineeships

Apart from the aforementioned ECHE, European Strategy for Universities, and the Digital Education Action Plan, there are four more policy resources worth mentioning given their recent spotlight and potential to further the improvement of Erasmus+ traineeships: the Proposal for Traineeship Directive, the proposal for a Council recommendation on a reinforced framework for traineeships, the Youth Guarantee and Youth Employment Initiative.

2.3.1 Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a Reinforced Quality Framework for Traineeships

The Proposal for a Council Recommendation on a Reinforced Quality Framework for Traineeships (European Commission, COM(2024) 133 final 2024/0069(NLE), 2024) aims to provide comprehensive guidelines that ensure traineeships offer valuable learning experiences while protecting the rights of trainees.

The proposal highlights the importance of formal written agreements between trainees and host organisations. These agreements, akin to a roadmap, clearly outline the duration, objectives, tasks, and expected outcomes of the traineeship. By setting transparent expectations, these agreements ensure that both parties understand their roles and responsibilities, paving the way for a structured and purposeful experience.

Central to the proposal is the focus on defined learning objectives. Each traineeship should have goals that align with the trainee's educational background and career aspirations, ensuring that the experience contributes meaningfully to their professional development. This approach transforms traineeships from mere work experiences into opportunities for substantial personal and professional growth.

Adequate supervision and mentoring are also key components of the proposal. Host organisations are encouraged to provide dedicated supervisors who can offer regular feedback and support. These mentors are not just task managers but guides who help trainees navigate their professional journeys, enhancing the overall quality of the learning experience.

Financial stability is crucial for trainees, and the proposal advocates for fair remuneration. This includes financial compensation and access to benefits such as training and professional development opportunities, creating a balanced and supportive environment for learning. The emphasis on fair remuneration ensures that trainees are not left to bear the costs of their work experiences alone. To prevent the misuse of traineeships as cheap labour, the proposal includes provisions ensuring that traineeships do not replace regular employment positions. This safeguard protects both the integrity of the traineeship and the rights of the trainee, ensuring they are engaged in genuine learning activities rather than performing the duties of regular employees.

Social protection is another vital aspect addressed by the proposal. Ensuring that trainees have access to essential protections like healthcare and insurance is particularly important for cross-border placements. This provision offers peace of mind, allowing trainees to focus on their professional growth without worrying about their basic needs.

The proposal also introduces mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the implementation of these guidelines. Member States are recommended to regularly report on the quality and outcomes of traineeships and establish complaint procedures for trainees to voice any concerns. These mechanisms contribute to making the guidelines upheld and having traineeships that are beneficial and fair.

2.3.2 Proposal for a Traineeships Directive

Complementing the Council Recommendation, the European Commission also proposed a Directive (European Commission, COM(2024) 132 final/2 2024/0068(COD), 2024) aimed at improving and enforcing the working conditions of trainees and combating the practice of disguising regular employment relationships as traineeships. This directive aims to offer a legal framework designed to protect the rights of trainees and ensure fair working conditions.

The directive proposal aims to distinguish between genuine traineeships and disguised employment relationships. By setting strict criteria for what constitutes a traineeship, the directive ensures that such positions are primarily educational and developmental, rather than being used as a source of cheap labour.

To ensure compliance, the directive introduces enforcement mechanisms, including regular inspections and penalties for non-compliance. These measures deter host organisations from exploiting trainees and encourage adherence to established standards. The directive

outlines specific rights and protections for trainees, including fair remuneration, reasonable working hours, and access to social protections such as healthcare and insurance. These provisions ensure that trainees are treated fairly and with respect, creating a supportive environment for their professional development.

Transparency and accountability are crucial components of the directive. Host organisations are required to provide detailed descriptions of traineeship conditions, including tasks, supervision arrangements, and learning objectives. This transparency ensures that trainees are fully aware of their rights and expectations, fostering an environment of trust and fairness. The directive also encourages Member States to establish support structures for trainees, including complaint mechanisms and advisory services. These structures provide trainees with resources and assistance if they encounter issues during their traineeship, ensuring they have avenues for support and redress.

2.3.3 The Youth Guarantee and the Youth Employment Initiative (YEI)

The Youth Guarantee and the Youth Employment Initiative (YEI) are additional policy instruments that support Erasmus+ traineeships.

The Youth Guarantee represents an important commitment by all EU Member States to support young people under the age of 30 in securing quality employment, continued education, apprenticeships, or traineeships within four months of becoming unemployed or leaving education. Initiated through a Council Recommendation in October 2020 (Council of the EU, (2020/C 372/01), 2020), the reinforced Youth Guarantee builds on this commitment, aiming to address the challenges exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Since its inception, the Youth Guarantee has been a transformative force in the European job market. Over the past several years, it has created numerous opportunities for young people and driven significant structural reforms and innovations within public employment services (PES). The programme has successfully reduced the number of young people not in employment, education, or training (NEETs) by approximately 1.7 million across the EU. By February 2020, youth unemployment had dropped to a record low of 14.9%, just before the pandemic-induced lockdowns took effect. This remarkable achievement underscores the substantial impact of the Youth Guarantee, which has enabled over 24 million young people to engage in employment, continued education, apprenticeships, and traineeships (European Parliament, 2021).

The reinforced Youth Guarantee adopts tailored, individualised approaches to support young people. It provides the necessary guidance to help them navigate the current job market, which has been reshaped by the pandemic. This includes finding crash courses or boot camps for upskilling if needed. These approaches take into account local labour market conditions and the opportunities presented by the accelerating digital and green transitions.

Significantly, the reinforced Youth Guarantee is backed by substantial EU financing through NextGenerationEU and the long-term EU budget. The European Union provides policy support and facilitates mutual learning activities to help Member States strengthen their infrastructure and measures for the reinforced Youth Guarantee. Additionally, the EU monitors progress across Member States to ensure the effective implementation of this initiative.

The Youth Employment Initiative (YEI) provides financial support to regions with high youth unemployment and helps funding traineeship opportunities and other initiatives aimed at improving youth employment prospects. The YEI (European Commission, COM(2015) 46 final 2015/0026 (COD), 2015) has been a relevant financial mechanism supporting the implementation of the Youth Guarantee across the European Union.

During the 2021-2023 period, the YEI received additional funding under the REACT-EU initiative, allowing Member States to enhance their support for young people affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. This financial boost was crucial in addressing the increased challenges faced by youth during the crisis.

For the 2021-2027 programming period, the YEI was integrated into the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+). This integration streamlines funding mechanisms while maintaining a strong focus on youth employment. Member States with higher NEET rates are required to allocate at least 12.5% of their ESF+ resources to youth employment initiatives. This ensures that targeted actions and structural reforms continue to support young people effectively. (European Commission, [The Reinforced Youth Guarantee](#)).

European Union policies, designed to enhance mobility, inclusiveness, and employability, have significantly impacted how traineeships are perceived and experienced across the EU. As the Erasmus+ programme evolves, understanding the tangible effects of these policies on the ground becomes increasingly important, particularly in light of the challenges faced by trainees during their mobility periods.

2.4 Impact of policies on Erasmus+ traineeships

The subsequent section delves into the data and insights derived from key surveys, particularly the ESNsurvey and Eurobarometer reports, to have an overview of the successes and shortcomings of the current policy frameworks, offering a critical analysis of how well these policies align with the needs and expectations of Erasmus+ trainees. This will allow us to highlight both the progress made and the areas where further policy enhancements are necessary to fully realise the potential of Erasmus+ Traineeships across Europe. This section will complement some of the findings identified in Part 1 of the desk research by adding data deriving from the direct surveying of students' perceptions of their traineeship experience.

2.4.1 Erasmus Student Network (ESN) Surveys

The impact of European Union policies on Erasmus+ Traineeships is evident through a variety of factors, from increased participation rates to the evolving support structures offered to participants. According to the XIV Edition of the ESNsurvey (ESN, 2022), the Erasmus+ programme, which is central to the European Union's mobility strategy, has seen significant developments over the years. The survey highlights that despite the improvements, there are still substantial areas needing attention, particularly in terms of the quality and comprehensiveness of support services for trainees. The disparities between Erasmus+ study and traineeship mobilities are particularly concerning. Trainees, unlike their study counterparts, often miss out on critical integration activities, such as Welcome Week events and buddy systems. This lack of support contributes to lower satisfaction rates among trainees compared to those engaged in Erasmus+ studies.

The XIV ESNsurvey also reveals that while international students are generally satisfied with host services, critical areas such as accommodation and local integration remain problematic. These aspects are crucial for enhancing the inclusiveness and overall experience of Erasmus+ traineeships. There have been some recent efforts to address these issues, such as the inclusion of accommodation support as a criterion in the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education evaluation. However, more targeted measures are needed to further progress, particularly in promoting local integration, which is vital for achieving the inclusion and democratic participation priorities outlined in the Erasmus+ programme.

The XV ESNsurvey's preliminary report (ESN, 2023) underscores that the most pressing challenges for Erasmus+ participants (both mobile students and mobile trainees) include insufficient funding to cover living costs and difficulties in securing affordable accommodation. These issues have only intensified over time, exacerbated by delays in the disbursement of grants and scholarships. The report also notes an increase in integration challenges with local students, further complicating the experience for many trainees. The cumulative data from both surveys (and the trends identified through the previous ESN Surveys) indicate that while policies have positively influenced the Erasmus+ programme's reach and scope, significant gaps remain in the quality of support, especially for trainees who face unique challenges during their mobility periods.

2.4.2 Insights from the Eurobarometer

The Flash Eurobarometer 523 with its survey conducted in March 2023 (DG COMM, 2023) sheds significant light on the experiences of young people with traineeships across the EU, including those related to the Erasmus+ programme. The findings from this survey are critical in understanding the broader impact of policies on Erasmus+ Traineeships, particularly in relation to how these experiences influence labour market integration.

One of the key insights from the Eurobarometer survey is the high prevalence of traineeship participation among young people. A remarkable 78% of respondents across the EU reported having undertaken at least one traineeship. Despite the limited pool of respondents, this data can be taken to indicate an increasing uptake of traineeships, which aligns with the objectives of various EU policies aimed at enhancing employability and professional skills among youth.

(DG COMM, 2023, figure on number of traineeships completed by students or graduates (excluding regular jobs) – percentage by country, page 10)

The survey also highlights the diversity in the types of traineeships undertaken. The largest proportion of traineeships, 44%, are part of academic or vocational qualifications, reflecting the significant role that education systems play in facilitating these opportunities. Additionally, 27% of traineeships serve as mandatory introductions to professional practice in specific fields, while 17% are linked to public employment programmes designed to help young people find work (Nuyts & Matthaes, 2023).

Practical placements are invaluable additions to a degree. Firstly, experiencing the world of work gives students insight into what long-term employment looks like. In that way, the very reason why students have selected their institution is gratified: As can be seen in the 2024 Global Student Experience Report (ETIO, 2024), “future career impact” has been consistently the number one factor in students’ decision-making since 2018. Secondly, supporting and encouraging students to complete practical placements and create a professional network is a direct way to build, maintain or improve a university’s reputation: “Making good contacts for the future” was topped as why a student would recommend their institution.

In terms of remuneration, the survey provides important data on the financial aspects of traineeships. Approximately 55% of respondents who had completed a traineeship reported receiving some form of payment or financial compensation, with significant variation across Member States. For instance, while 78% of respondents in Croatia received remuneration, only 39% of those in Belgium did. Interestingly, the likelihood of receiving payment also correlated with the length of the traineeship, with longer traineeships being more likely to be paid.

The survey findings also underscore the barriers to accessing cross-border traineeships, a critical component of Erasmus+ opportunities. Financial constraints remain the most significant barrier, with 30% of respondents citing insufficient financial resources as a key obstacle. This highlights the ongoing need for supportive policies to ensure equitable access to these valuable opportunities across socio-economic groups.

The high participation rates, coupled with the financial challenges and varying types of traineeships, suggest that while progress has been made in integrating traineeships into the education and employment landscape, there is still room for policy improvements, particularly in ensuring equitable access and adequate financial support for all participants.

Additionally, 22% of respondents of the survey mentioned that they were not well-informed about opportunities for traineeships in other EU countries. This data underscores the need for continued policy support to address these financial and informational gaps, which limit the effectiveness of the Erasmus+ Traineeships programme in achieving its mobility goals.

In terms of learning outcomes, the survey indicates that most young people have a positive view of the educational benefits of their traineeships. About 75% of respondents agreed that they learned professionally useful skills during their last traineeship, and 66% felt that their traineeship was helpful in finding a job afterwards. These findings suggest that, despite existing challenges, traineeships under the Erasmus+ framework are generally effective in enhancing employability, which aligns with the broader goals of EU policies.

When integrated with data from the ESN surveys discussed previously, the results of the Flash Eurobarometer 523 survey offer a further clue on the impact that policies have on the Erasmus traineeship experience, revealing both successes and areas where further support is needed to enhance the quality and inclusiveness of traineeships across Europe.

These findings which focus specifically on traineeships were already noticed within the the Flash Eurobarometer 502 report, focusing on Youth and Democracy in the European Year of Youth, which provided a revealing perspective on how young people view traineeships as part of broader European initiatives (DG EAC & DG COMM, 2022). Notably, it highlights that traineeships are not just an isolated educational tool but a significant element in the overall strategy to engage youth in the democratic and economic fabric of the EU.

The survey reveals that young people across Europe see traineeships as a critical opportunity for skill acquisition, career development, and a bridge to long-term employment. However, concerns about the quality and accessibility of these opportunities persist, reflecting broader anxieties about the transition from education to the labour market.

The perception of traineeships is heavily influenced by socio-economic factors. Respondents from disadvantaged backgrounds express a lower level of confidence in their ability to access high-quality traineeships, indicating that more needs to be done to ensure inclusiveness and equal opportunities across member states. This highlights the importance of initiatives like the reinforced Youth Guarantee, which aims to address these disparities by ensuring all young people receive an offer of employment, education, apprenticeship, or traineeship within a set timeframe.

Furthermore, the survey underscores the critical role of EU policy in shaping these experiences. It is evident that young people expect EU initiatives, such as Erasmus+, to provide more than just academic opportunities; they also seek meaningful, paid work experiences that can lead to sustainable employment. This expectation aligns with ongoing efforts to enhance the quality framework for traineeships, which is vital for maintaining the credibility and attractiveness of these programmes across Europe.

2.5 Challenges and barriers

Part of the desk research addressed the challenges faced in the context of trainees building on available literature and research on the topic, the following section will provide further insights from a policy-centred angle and zooming in specifically in the EU context.

A recent study by Alcidi et al. (Alcidi et. al., 2024) offers a useful overview and insights that connect with the policy developments identified above.

The research aligns with key points of the ESN survey and the Eurobarometer highlighting how the Erasmus+ Traineeships programme is intricately woven into the broader political and legal landscape of the European Union's employment and education policies. The work by Alcidi shows how initiatives like the Youth Guarantee and Erasmus+ are at the heart of the EU's efforts to boost youth employability and promote cross-border mobility. Despite the strides made in expanding opportunities through Erasmus+ Traineeships, significant challenges remain. One of the main issues is the inconsistent quality of traineeships across different Member States. In some cases, traineeships are misused, with trainees being treated as cheap labour rather than receiving meaningful educational experiences. This exploitation is particularly troubling in situations where the lines between a true traineeship and regular employment are blurred, leaving trainees overworked and underpaid without the appropriate legal protections or fair compensation.

Moreover, access to high-quality traineeships is not equal, with socio-economic disparities limiting opportunities for those from disadvantaged backgrounds. These challenges underscore the need for a more cohesive and robust policy framework to ensure that all trainees, regardless of their background, can equally benefit from the Erasmus+ programme. The complexities of these challenges are deeply tied to the varying regulatory environments across Member States, which often lack clarity and consistency, making it difficult to enforce standards and protect trainees from such exploitative practices.

Another major challenge lies in the poor quality of many traineeships, particularly when it comes to working conditions and the educational value they provide. The study reveals that about half of all traineeships in the EU are unpaid, and many trainees lack access to essential social protections. This lack of financial and social security not only diminishes the traineeship experience but also limits participation to those who can afford to work without pay, further deepening social inequalities. Moreover, the study highlights a

concerning statistic: over 20% of trainees report that the skills they gained during their traineeships were not professionally useful, casting doubt on the effectiveness of these programmes in truly enhancing employability.

Access to high-quality traineeships is another significant issue, especially for individuals from vulnerable groups. These groups often encounter barriers such as financial constraints, insufficient information, and limited opportunities for cross-border traineeships. These challenges are particularly severe in the case of unpaid traineeships, where the absence of remuneration and social protections further discourages participation from disadvantaged backgrounds. While remote and hybrid traineeships offer the potential to widen access, they also introduce new challenges, particularly in maintaining high standards of training and supervision, which are critical for the overall success and value of the traineeship experience. Moreover, although remote or hybrid traineeships can make it easier for people to participate by removing the need to relocate, it doesn't solve the problem of unpaid work. Even when someone participates remotely in a traineeship with an organisation in a different country, they still have financial needs, and being unpaid or underpaid remains a barrier.

In other words, simply staying at home doesn't remove all the financial burdens. While remote work might reduce some costs (like travel or relocation), trainees still have living expenses (like rent, food, and internet). If a remote traineeship is unpaid, it can still be unaffordable for people from disadvantaged backgrounds, so payment and social protections are just as important in remote or hybrid setups.

These challenges are further exacerbated by the complexities of national regulations governing traineeships, which vary widely across the EU. This inconsistency in the legal status of trainees, coupled with the inadequate enforcement of existing regulations and the limited capacity for monitoring and inspections, creates an environment where trainees can easily be exploited or neglected. The study stresses that these issues require coordinated action at the EU level to standardise practices, enhance protections, and ensure that all traineeships offer meaningful learning experiences that truly improve employability.

The extent of these problems differs from one country to another, with some Member States reporting higher instances of problematic traineeships. This disparity underscores the need for EU-level intervention to harmonise standards and ensure that all Member States adhere to best practices in the management of traineeships.

2.5.1 The regulatory limitations

For analysing the regulatory frameworks surrounding youth employment in the EU, Helme's study on the problems and paradoxes found in the EU's regulation on traineeships (Helme, 2024) provides critical insights into the areas of improvements. This study is particularly relevant as it delves into the inherent contradictions and gaps in the existing legislation, highlighting how these regulatory shortcomings exacerbate the vulnerable status of trainees across the EU.

The study emphasises the hollow nature of the current traineeship regulations, where the legal status of a trainee is recognised, yet devoid of substantive rights. This paradox is central to understanding the broader issues within youth employment policies, as it underscores a systemic failure to provide adequate protections and rights to young workers. The analysis in the paper reveals that the Quality Framework on Traineeships (QFT), although a significant step, remains insufficient due to its non-binding nature and limited scope, particularly as it excludes most types of traineeships from its protections.

Furthermore, the paper by Helme explores the implications of the EU Court of Justice's (CJEU) case-law, which in various instances conflicts with the QFT, particularly in cases where trainees may be classified as workers but are denied the associated rights. This discrepancy is especially important with Erasmus+ Trainees as it highlights a critical area of concern for policymakers and stakeholders involved in youth employment, as it exposes young workers to potential exploitation under the guise of learning experiences.

The study provides a relevant analysis of the current regulatory landscape and its exploration of alternative approaches. The analysis' results presents a re-evaluation of the traineeship status, proposing that trainees should be recognised as workers with additional rights, thereby reversing the current trend of excluding them from the full protections of labour law, which synergises with the aims of the Reinforced Quality Framework for Traineeships and the related Directive proposals mentioned previously. Once again, the main argument that this reflection leads to is that the current EU regulations on traineeships are inadequate and need substantial reform.

2.5.2 Looking for a solutions

The need for EU action is strongly influenced by the cross-border nature of the Erasmus+ programme and the inconsistent standards of traineeships across different Member States. The EU's role goes beyond merely setting standards: it involves providing the necessary support and oversight to ensure these standards are consistently upheld. The legal basis

for EU involvement is firmly established, with treaties and regulations laying the groundwork for intervention in education and employment matters. The true value of EU participation lies in its capacity to coordinate efforts across Member States, ensuring that the advantages of traineeships are distributed fairly and that the quality of these experiences remains high.

The objectives of EU policy interventions in traineeships are well-defined: to enhance the quality, accessibility, and effectiveness of these opportunities. As highlighted in the policy analysis, this includes preventing the misuse of traineeships by ensuring they are not exploited as substitutes for regular employment. Additionally, improving the working conditions for trainees—ensuring fair pay and access to social protections—is a key goal. Another vital objective is to make traineeships more inclusive, ensuring that all young people, regardless of their socio-economic background, have access to these valuable opportunities.

To address these challenges, a range of policy options is available (Alcidi et. al., 2024). These options include non-binding measures, such as guidelines and recommendations, as well as binding legislative actions that would require Member States to adhere to stricter standards. One of the key proposals is the establishment of a reinforced Quality Framework for Traineeships, which would set minimum standards for all traineeships within the EU. This framework would ensure that traineeships offer fair remuneration, clear learning objectives, and proper supervision, guaranteeing that these opportunities provide real educational value.

Another approach is to strengthen the monitoring and enforcement of existing regulations, making sure that employers who do not meet the required standards are held accountable. This could involve introducing penalties for non-compliance and creating mechanisms for trainees to report any abuses they encounter. The potential impact of these policy options is significant. By improving the quality of traineeships, the EU can enhance the employability of young people, helping them transition more effectively from education to the workforce. This, in turn, could lead to a reduction in youth unemployment and NEET (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) rates across the EU.

However, the implementation of these policies also comes with costs. Ensuring compliance with higher standards may require additional resources, both for employers and for public authorities tasked with monitoring and enforcement. Despite these costs, the long-term benefits of a well-regulated traineeship system are clear, including a more skilled and adaptable workforce and a reduction in youth unemployment.

Main evaluation conclusions	Study
<p>Relevance: the QFT is highly relevant to fostering the labour market integration of young people. A lesson from the pandemic is that adjustment may be needed to make sure the QFT remains relevant in a context of more remote work. Mixed views on the relevance of the non-binding nature of the QFT and on the relevance to add remuneration and social protection in the QFT principles.</p>	<p>Policy measures on fair remuneration and access to social protection are proposed, as well as measures to facilitate remote/hybrid traineeships and promote their quality.</p>
<p>Effectiveness: The principles of the QFT have been enshrined to a moderate degree in national legislation/frameworks for traineeships. Even when national legislation shows high implementation of the QFT, this does not always translate to quality traineeships on the ground, due to lack of enforcement and monitoring. There have been improvements in the quality of traineeships since 2014 but inequalities remain in terms of access to opportunities to undertake traineeships.</p>	<p>Policy measures to improve working conditions and increase transparency on the learning content are proposed. Policy measures to ensure accessibility to persons with disability and the inclusiveness of traineeships to all vulnerable groups are proposed. Policy measures to determine problematic traineeships and to strengthen inspections and enforcement are proposed. Accompanying measures are proposed on awareness raising, data collection and monitoring and further stakeholder involvement.</p>
<p>Efficiency: Overall the adjustment costs for employers linked to supervising trainees, assessing and certifying trainees' skills, and developing training plans were assessed as small, likely to be more significant for small organisations. The QFT implied enforcement costs for authorities for designing and implementing new legislation and for labour inspection. Overall, costs are lower than benefits and the administrative burden is low.</p>	<p>The policy measures will be designed to minimise additional administrative costs and other costs for businesses and authorities.</p>
<p>Coherence: There is a fairly good level of coherence with the national policies especially on employment policies for ALMPs. There is good level of coherence with other relevant EU initiatives, funds and programmes.</p>	<p>The policy measures will enhance coherence by covering all four types of traineeships, all trainees and further aligning with existing national and EU initiatives.</p>
<p>EU added value: the QFT provides an EU-level structure and framework for national authorities and policymakers although the full EU added value is limited by weak implementation.</p>	<p>Policy measures are proposed to improve the implementation, monitoring and enforcement of the QFT and increase its EU added value.</p>

(Alcidi et. al. 2024, Table 59: How the study addresses the evaluation conclusions page 221)

In the context of youth unemployment in Europe, O'Reilly et al. (O'Reilly et al., 2015) provided a further in-depth analysis of the multifaceted challenges that young people face in the labour market at the time and that still are relevant today despite the policy actions currently present to tackle these. The study identified five core characteristics that shape the current landscape of youth unemployment: increased labour market flexibility, expansion of education leading to skill mismatches, extensive youth migration, the influence of family legacies, and the significant role of EU policy initiatives. Let's now briefly unpack each of these 5 core characteristics.

One of the most critical challenges highlighted by O'Reilly et al.. is the increasing labour market flexibility, which, while intended to boost employment, often results in precarious job conditions for young people. This flexibility, while benefiting companies, manifests in the high prevalence of temporary and part-time contracts, particularly among youth,

which leads to job insecurity, lower wages, and limited access to benefits such as social security and pensions. This scenario creates a cohort effect, where younger generations face prolonged risks of unstable employment, ultimately leading to long-term career and financial challenges.

Moreover, O'Reilly et al. show argue that the expansion of education has not aligned well with the evolving needs of the labour market, leading to a significant skills mismatch. Many young people find themselves unable to secure employment that matches their qualifications. This mismatch not only results in underemployment but also contributes to lower job satisfaction and wage penalties, further exacerbating the difficulties faced by the youth in achieving economic stability.

Highly relevant in the framework of Erasmus+ intra-European Union movement, the phenomenon of disparities in economic conditions and employment opportunities across Member States is relevant. While free movement can offer better job prospects, it might come at the cost of accepting jobs below one's qualifications, which can hinder career development and long-term employability.

Family legacies also play a crucial role in shaping youth employment outcomes. The study in fact showcases how intergenerational unemployment can perpetuate cycles of disadvantage, where the economic struggles of parents influence the job prospects and financial stability of their children. This dynamic further polarises opportunities for young people, depending on their family background and regional economic conditions.

Finally, the paper underscores the importance of EU policy initiatives, such as the Youth Guarantee, in addressing these challenges. However, the effectiveness of these policies heavily depends on their implementation at the national level, where variations in regulatory frameworks and economic conditions can either support or hinder their success.

Returning to the topic of the possible solution, to ensure the effectiveness of these policies, the importance of robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms is evident. This includes the collection of data on traineeships across the EU, allowing for the assessment of how well the policies are being implemented and where further improvements are needed. Stakeholder involvement is also crucial, with structured consultations and other collaborative spaces with employers, educational institutions, and trainees themselves to gather feedback and ensure that the policies remain relevant and effective.

2.6 Some case studies and initiatives

As we approach the recommendations section of the desk research, it is important to first look at a number of case studies and initiatives that demonstrate the varying challenges and opportunities across different regions and sectors. These examples will highlight how existing programmes, like Erasmus+ Traineeships, can benefit from ongoing efforts and identify areas where further improvement is needed. By exploring these initiatives and observing their synergies with DETAS, we aim to uncover best practices, and potential strategies to enhance the quality and accessibility of Erasmus+ Traineeships, particularly in light of ongoing policy developments and emerging trends in digital transformation, youth employment, and market needs.

2.6.1 The West Balkans case

This case study by the Regional Cooperation Council (Regional Cooperation Council, 2021) provides an in-depth analysis of the youth employment landscape in the Western Balkans which can contribute to understanding the areas where Erasmus+ Traineeships can benefit and the challenges that these traineeships would need to address. Key issues highlighted which contribute to a precarious labour market situation for young people include the persistently high rates of youth unemployment, which have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic and underlined the need to increase the number of available Erasmus+ Traineeships.

The study sheds light on the structural problems within the education systems, which often fail to equip young people with the skills required by the labour market. This mismatch results in prolonged transitions from education to employment, further hindering young people's ability to secure stable jobs. Additionally, the prevalence of temporary and insecure employment contracts contributes to a sense of uncertainty among the youth, affecting both their well-being and economic productivity. In this context, the integration of Erasmus+ Traineeships is a positive factor which would need to be upscaled quantitatively.

Furthermore, the study discusses the gender disparities in youth employment, where young women face greater challenges in accessing the labour market, often due to inadequate support for balancing work and family responsibilities. The research underscores the need for targeted policies, such as the introduction of Youth Guarantee schemes, which have shown promise in some areas like North Macedonia, to address these challenges effectively. This would mean that Erasmus+ Traineeships can further improve and provide more benefits by increasing focus on gender inclusion elements. It would also gain from a research perspective by tracking not only quantitatively but also qualitatively the reasons why based on gender a different motivation arises in joining (or not) a Traineeship opportunity.

2.6.2 The Bulgarian case

Another case study by Jeliazkova et. al. (Jeliazkova et. al., 2018) once again on youth employment policies but this time in Bulgaria provides another valuable perspective on the complex challenges and mixed outcomes of labour market interventions aimed at young people in a post-transition economy which can help once again understand how Erasmus+ traineeships can solve to tackle the barriers to traineeships and by extension to employment. Bulgaria, like many other countries in Eastern Europe, has faced significant hurdles in adapting its labour market and social policies to the realities of a rapidly changing economic landscape. This historical context is crucial to understanding why youth unemployment remains stubbornly high and why the proportion of NEETs is alarmingly large.

One of the most striking insights from this analysis of Jeliazkova et. al. is the persistent vulnerability of youth in the Bulgarian labour market. Despite numerous policy initiatives, young people, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds, continue to face significant barriers to securing stable and meaningful employment. The study highlights that while there have been some successes - especially among better-educated youth - many of the active labour market policies (ALMPs) have fallen short of their goals. ALMPs are government programs that intervene in the labour market to assist not only the unemployed in finding work but also the underemployed and those seeking better job opportunities. These measures often provide only short-term relief and fail to address the underlying structural issues that prevent young people from fully integrating into the labour market. The repercussions for EU policies and the Erasmus+ programme are evident and exacerbated by the fact that EU policies face the challenge of the need to harmonise the situation between Member States and adapt to different national legal contexts preventing a one solution that can fit all situations.

The implementation of these policies in the Bulgarian case has been hindered by several key challenges. One major issue is the broad targeting of ALMPs, which has led to what the study describes as a creaming effect. In essence, the policies tend to benefit those young people who are already in a better position to succeed - those with higher levels of education or who are more easily accessible - while leaving behind those who are most in need of support, such as individuals from marginalised communities or with lower educational attainment. This selective benefit undermines the overall effectiveness of the interventions and exacerbates existing inequalities. The creaming effect is something that is to be considered with Erasmus+ Traineeships where the risk of this type of marginalisation is not only present at the national level with Rural vs Urban areas situations but also between member states who have different socio-economic situations and whereby potential trainees from one country might have disadvantages in accessing these opportunities.

Moreover, the study critiques the fragmented nature of Bulgaria's policy framework, where labour market policies are often implemented in isolation from social policies and once again this is something that EU policies ought to benefit from, even though this is less noticeable at the EU level where the harmonisation efforts already lead policies to consider the different national contexts in which they would be implemented. This lack of coordination in the Bulgarian case results in missed opportunities to address the broader socio-economic factors that contribute to youth unemployment. For instance, without a robust support system that includes both employment and social services, young people from disadvantaged backgrounds are less likely to benefit from employment programs, no matter how well-designed these programs might be in isolation.

The recommendations provided in the study are both practical and forward-thinking. It advocates for a more targeted approach in the design and implementation of ALMPs, one that focuses specifically on interventions proven to work for the most vulnerable groups. Furthermore, it calls for a systemic shift towards better integration of labour market policies with social policies, emphasising the need for coordinated efforts to address not just unemployment, but the root causes of social and economic exclusion. This includes a stronger focus on creating quality jobs that offer young people not just employment, but opportunities for career progression and long-term stability. This is in line with the needs at the EU level proposed within the policy efforts for a Reinforced Quality Framework for Traineeships and therefore these needs synergy opens the door for practical learning experiences from case studies like the Bulgarian one.

2.6.3 The SPRINT project (Standardize Best PRactices about INTernships)

The SPRINT project (Standardize Best PRactices about INTernships, <https://www.sprint-erasmusplus.fr/>) has been an EU-funded project aimed at improving the integration of young people into the labour market through the development of a European Quality Framework for Internships. Running from September 2017 to December 2020, the project was co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme and involved seven partner organisations from across Europe, including universities, youth organisations, trade unions, and employers. The central goal of the SPRINT project was to create a recognised and standardised quality framework for internships that could be applied across Europe, ensuring that internships provide meaningful educational experiences, protect the rights of trainees, and meet the needs of host organisations.

The SPRINT European Quality Framework for Internships provided a foundation to improve quality standards for traineeships. SPRINT developed criteria such as fair remuneration, skills development, and social protection, standardised practices to contribute to aligning Erasmus+ traineeships with the highest quality standards across all participating host organisations.

Moreover, the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) created by SPRINT on European Criteria for Quality Internships offers eight key quality indicators, including recruitment, tutoring, and career development. These indicators can serve as a concrete guide for the implementation of high-quality traineeships allowing actors to build upon these indicators reflecting the changing needs of the labour market and the increasing focus on digital transformation and remote work, as highlighted in the Digital Education Action Plan.

2.6.4 Digital4Business

The Digital4Business project (<https://digital4business.eu/>) (D4B) aimed at creating a pan-European Masters programme aimed at developing advanced digital skills across a range of industries, with a strong focus on supporting SMEs and promoting long-term competitiveness and growth in the European labour market. Launched in 2022, this initiative merges academia and industry to address the growing digital skills gap by providing high-demand qualifications in areas such as AI, cybersecurity, and data analytics.

Even if the focus of the project has been on the academic pathway rather than the traineeship once, it focused on upskilling young professionals and creating a market-led

framework for development which is relevant for traineeship and University-Business cooperation (UBC) to bridge the gap between the two foster employment through quality traineeships. The project is dedicated to equipping business professionals and graduates with the necessary digital expertise, aiming to meet the evolving needs of the European economy and to create a bridge between educational institutions and businesses.

The Digital4Business framework integrated the insights gained from the project's needs analysis identified the digital skills gaps across EU countries providing a toolset to support Erasmus+ Traineeships to produce graduates who are not only academically proficient but also skilled in critical digital domains.

Additionally, Digital4Business' focus on industry collaboration - with courses co-created by companies and universities - making it easier to leverage the industry-academia partnerships to enhance the practical relevance of traineeships, ensuring that they address both the technical and soft skills needed for the future workforce.

Another beneficial output of the project is the modular learning approach which includes flexible, part-time, and full-time online formats, complemented by physical workshops and networking events. This could inspire further pilot innovations in the Erasmus+ programme, allowing for greater accessibility, different types of traineeships, and the inclusion of micro-credentials that recognise specific skills trainees acquire during their placements.

2.7 Global Alliance for YOUth

The Global Alliance for YOUth (<https://www.globalallianceforyouth.org/homepage>) is a collaborative effort among 25 international private companies, united by the goal of empowering young people in the workplace. With over 1.5 million employees globally, the alliance has made a commitment to supporting youth through initiatives that offer first job experiences, run educational programs, and promote young entrepreneurship. Since 2019, these companies have collectively provided over 30 million development opportunities for young people worldwide, making a significant impact on youth employability.

The Global Alliance for YOUth opens a window to understand how the business sector can play a transformative role in supporting youth employment. The Global Alliance's mission is to address the skills gap and improve youth employability serving as a real-world example of how corporate initiatives can complement educational frameworks, offering young people both the skills and practical opportunities they need to transition successfully into the labour market.

The Global Alliance's efforts thus offer best practices that these companies have established, particularly in the areas of digital skills development and entrepreneurship. The focus on helping young people navigate a rapidly changing work environment and preparing them for the future of work aims to create a standardised, high-quality traineeship experience recognising the need for innovative approaches to youth employment, particularly in the wake of challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic, which has disproportionately affected young people.

In addition, the Global Alliance for YOUth brings to the table a strong network of industry partners that could potentially enrich the Erasmus+ traineeship ecosystem by offering new partnerships and cross-border opportunities. The business-led focus of the Global Alliance also ensures that the skills being developed in these programs are directly aligned with market needs.

2.8 Improving traineeship through quality standards

High-quality traineeships are the cornerstone of a successful mobility experience, bridging the gap between academic learning and professional practice. To ensure that Erasmus+ traineeships deliver equitable, inclusive, and impactful experiences, the following standards have been proposed, addressing the most pressing challenges identified during our research. These recommendations aim to enhance the accessibility, structure, and value of traineeships, fostering meaningful learning opportunities while upholding fairness and transparency for all participants. Drawing on survey data, focus group insights, and the collective expertise of the DETAS project consortium, this section outlines a comprehensive set of quality benchmarks. These standards focus on key areas such as fair compensation, inclusive practices, robust support structures, and effective career development pathways, ensuring that traineeships not only meet but exceed the expectations of both trainees and host organisations.

Fair compensation

A key barrier to participation in Erasmus+ traineeships is financial strain, particularly for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. A minimum compensation system, calibrated to local living costs, is essential to cover fundamental expenses such as food, accommodation, and transportation. Targeted grants for financially vulnerable students should ensure no one is excluded from this transformative experience.

In addition, employers should clearly communicate compensation details, including the breakdown of allowances and support offered, to improve transparency and reduce uncertainty for trainees. Employers should also explore available EU funding, such as the European Social Fund+ (ESF+), to support trainee payments. Decoupling Erasmus grants from financial compensation can ensure that grants are viewed as a complementary form of support rather than a substitute for salary.

To foster long-term opportunities, financial incentives could be offered to employers who hire interns permanently following their placements. Employers should also consider accommodation arrangements for trainees, particularly for those with disabilities, ensuring that accessible housing is integrated into pre-departure planning. This effort must be accompanied by clear communication of support available to students with disabilities.

Inclusion and accessibility

To ensure Erasmus+ traineeships are accessible to all students, especially those with disabilities or from marginalised backgrounds, this dedicated standard focuses on fostering an inclusive environment throughout the traineeship process.

Employers and sending institutions must actively promote accessible housing and facilities and incorporate these considerations into pre-departure planning. Workplace accessibility should be ensured, including accommodations such as assistive technology, adjusted workspaces, or flexible work arrangements tailored to individual needs.

Training and awareness initiatives for host organisation staff are essential to build a culture of inclusion. These initiatives should cover accessibility practices, training, and practical guidance on working with students with disabilities, ensuring the workplace is welcoming and supportive.

Inclusion efforts should also prioritise clear communication between all stakeholders (students, host organisations, and sending institutions). This includes explicit guidelines on accessibility resources, workplace adjustments, and support systems available during the traineeship. Ongoing monitoring and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to assess the success of inclusion efforts.

Enhanced pre-departure and on-site support

Preparation remains a critical gap in many traineeship experiences. Comprehensive pre-departure programmes should equip students with the necessary tools to succeed, including financial management skills, housing guidance, and cultural adaptation strategies. These programmes must also address administrative processes, such as visa requirements, healthcare coverage, and understanding local laws.

Written agreements between all stakeholders should clearly outline roles, responsibilities, and expectations. Learning Agreements must be validated well in advance, ensuring all parties are aligned before the traineeship begins.

To support trainees during their placement, host organisations should assign designated mentors, properly trained in supervision. These mentors must provide structured feedback and guidance, addressing both professional and cultural integration needs. Regular check-ins should be conducted to ensure the traineeship remains on track and adjustments can be made if necessary.

Furthermore, host organisations and sending institutions should prioritise social and cultural integration by facilitating team-building activities or introductions to key colleagues. Providing trainees with information about their host city or region, such as cultural norms and practical tips, can enhance their overall experience.

Finally, resilience training for trainees and preparatory resources for sending institutions should be formalised. This includes tools to assess and measure a trainee's preparedness and well-being before and after the placement.

Structured learning objectives and transparency

Traineeships should align closely with the student's academic background and career goals. Clear learning objectives must be defined at the outset, focusing on measurable outcomes that are meaningful to both the trainee and the host organisation. These objectives should be revisited mid-placement to ensure alignment with the trainee's progress and integrated into written agreements such as the Learning Agreement.

Host organisations should provide detailed job descriptions that include specific tasks, expected skills development, and the relevance of the traineeship to the trainee's professional field. These descriptions must ensure that learning outcomes are substantial and go beyond routine or administrative tasks.

Transparency in the recruitment process is essential. Host organisations must offer clear and comprehensive information on compensation, working conditions, and accessibility, allowing trainees to fully understand their responsibilities and expectations before the placement begins. Flexibility in task design should be considered to allow for adjustments based on the trainee's strengths and career aspirations.

To promote equity, sending institutions should conduct quality checks on proposed traineeship tasks to ensure they align with the trainee's academic and professional goals. Additionally, provisions to safeguard intellectual property rights must be explicitly included in agreements, especially for placements involving research.

Social protections and wellbeing

Cross-border traineeships expose students to unique risks due to inadequate social protections. To ensure a secure and stress-free experience, trainees must be provided with comprehensive health, accident, and liability insurance, regardless of the placement

location. Sending institutions should ensure trainees are fully informed about the scope of their coverage, and any additional country-specific requirements must be clearly communicated during pre-departure preparations.

Employers should be encouraged to promote workplace safety and inclusivity by providing accessible facilities and accommodations tailored to the needs of trainees with disabilities. This includes addressing both physical accessibility and ensuring access to workplace adjustments or assistive technologies as required.

In addition to basic protections, emergency preparedness is crucial. Trainees must have access to detailed emergency contacts and procedures, including local emergency numbers and protocols to follow in the event of workplace incidents. Employers should be required to ensure a safe and supportive work environment but not bear the responsibility for insurance management, which remains the obligation of sending institutions.

Finally, ongoing monitoring of trainee well-being during the placement should be formalised. This includes regular check-ins by both the sending institution and host organisation to address any emerging concerns.

Contracts, duration, and transparent hiring practices

A well-defined contract is essential for ensuring a high-quality and fair traineeship experience. Comprehensive written agreements must clearly outline the roles, rights, and obligations of all stakeholders, including the trainee, the sending institution, and the host organisation. These agreements should explicitly detail the traineeship's objectives, duration, renewal conditions, and expected outcomes, ensuring the placement is time-bound and aligned with the trainee's academic and career goals. Contracts should also specify working hours, compensation, and leave policies, providing full clarity to trainees.

Host organisations must demonstrate transparency in their recruitment processes. This includes providing detailed information on staff-to-intern ratios, ensuring that traineeships are not used as a substitute for regular staff. Employers should implement reasonable intervals between hiring successive interns to avoid over-reliance on trainees for tasks that should be assigned to permanent employees.

Employers must ensure that trainees' tasks are substantive, aligned with learning objectives, and not exploitative. To support this, recruitment platforms should include mandatory fields for key contract details, such as compensation, working conditions, and

expected responsibilities, to promote transparency. Contracts could also incorporate provisions for feedback and evaluation, ensuring that trainees receive meaningful guidance and that employers maintain accountability for the quality of the placement. Sending institutions should oversee compliance with these standards, conducting periodic reviews to ensure that agreements align with transparent hiring practices and traineeship quality expectations.

Career development and post-placement recognition

Traineeships should bridge the gap between academic learning and full-time employment by providing meaningful career development opportunities. Host organisations must view traineeships as part of a talent pipeline, offering structured career development workshops, mentorship, and exposure to various professional roles within the organisation. Employers are encouraged to identify high-performing trainees and actively consider them for permanent roles, creating pathways to long-term opportunities.

To enhance the impact of traineeships, structured post-placement feedback must be provided to trainees. This includes a detailed evaluation of the skills developed during the placement, offering constructive insights into their performance and areas for growth. Trainees should also be supported in articulating these skills on professional platforms, such as LinkedIn or in their CVs, to improve employability.

Traineeships must be formally acknowledged as valid work experience in future recruitment processes. Employers and sending institutions should issue certificates or letters of recommendation that explicitly recognize the competencies gained. To standardise this, feedback forms and certificates can synergise and align more with the European Skills, Competences, Qualifications, and Occupations (ESCO) framework, ensuring consistency across placements.

Regarding post-traineeship alumni engagement, employers can be encouraged by sending institutions to maintain connections with former trainees through alumni networks or mentorship opportunities. Additionally, employers should provide guidance on career pathways within their sectors to help trainees navigate their future professional development.

Monitoring long-term outcomes of traineeships is essential. Sending institutions should track post-placement success rates, including job offers or further academic pursuits, and use this data to refine programme design.

Part 2 references

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PART 3

Data Analysis

3.1. Introduction

This third section of the desk research builds upon the foundation established in the preceding parts, synthesising the insights we uncovered to delve deeper into the digital dimension of Erasmus+ traineeships.

As we have seen, Part I offered a thorough review of the academic and professional literature on mobile traineeships, including the Erasmus+ programme. It examined the benefits and challenges of international mobility, drawing attention to the transformative potential of these experiences for trainees' personal and professional development. Part I scoped Erasmus+ in the broader context of mobility trends highlighting how such initiatives foster employability, intercultural competence, and academic growth.

Then, with Part II the focus was shifted to policies and practical case studies, illustrating how key mechanisms and strategies enable the success of mobility programmes. This section dissected the policy frameworks underpinning Erasmus+ and explored institutional practices that have proven effective in addressing challenges such as accessibility, inclusivity, and sustainability. Through real-world examples, we underscored the importance of robust support structures in enhancing the quality and equity of mobility opportunities.

Finally, with Part III we will transition to the digital infrastructure that supports these efforts, centring on ErasmusIntern.org, a pivotal platform in the ecosystem of Erasmus+ traineeships. This section analyses data from the platform, user surveys, and focus group discussions to understand how ErasmusIntern.org facilitates the mobility experience and where it can be enhanced. By doing so, we will bridge the theoretical and policy-oriented insights from earlier sections with the practical realities faced by users navigating international traineeships.

The analysis presented in this Part III draws from original research conducted within the DETAS project, encompassing a diverse range of methodologies designed to capture the realities of Erasmus+ traineeships. This includes data collected from ErasmusIntern.org's platform analytics, surveys administered to users of the platform, and qualitative insights from focus groups with past trainees. These findings were specifically gathered and analysed for the purposes of this report, providing a unique perspective on the digital infrastructure supporting Erasmus+ mobility. By integrating these sources, we aim to offer

a comprehensive view of how the ErasmusIntern platform facilitates international traineeships and identify opportunities for further enhancement.

3.1.1. Purpose of the analysis

What makes a platform truly transformative in the context of mobile traineeships? Is it its ability to connect applicants with opportunities? Or does its impact lie in its capacity to shape the trajectory of experiences before, during, and after a traineeship? These are the questions that this Part seeks to answer through an exploration of ErasmusIntern.org, a pivotal online platform to Erasmus+ traineeships.

This analysis takes a broader, strategic view of the Erasmus+ mobility experience, with a particular focus on the interplay between ErasmusIntern.org and the wider framework supporting international traineeships. ErasmusIntern.org is a digital platform launched in 2014 within the framework of the project STORY (Strengthening the Training Opportunities for International Youth). Erasmusintern.org provides a critical infrastructure for connecting trainees and recruiters. We will thus analyse the platform in light of the trajectory of the mobility journey. By integrating quantitative data, survey feedback, and qualitative insights, we will uncover broader trends and strategic opportunities that impact the success of traineeships.

The research draws from three complementary sources:

First, we will give an overview of an in-depth analysis of Erasmusintern.org's user data, focusing on patterns of engagement, application behaviours, and demographic trends. This will allow us to evaluate how the platform facilitates connections between trainees and recruiters and explores its evolving role in the digitalisation of mobility programmes.

As a second pillar of this part, we will analyse insights gathered from a wide-ranging survey of trainees users of Erasmusintern.org, capturing their experiences across all stages of the mobility process - pre-departure, on-site, and post-traineeship. We will evaluate satisfaction levels and highlight recurring challenges, offering a user-centric perspective on what works and where gaps remain and therefore where potential venues for improvement for the platform can be found.

Finally, the DETAS consortium gathered rich qualitative feedback from focus groups conducted with past trainees. These discussions provide a nuanced view of the mobility experience, delving into the logistical, cultural, and professional dimensions of

international placements. Unlike the platform-focused data, these sessions reveal insights into the broader realities of Erasmus+ traineeships.

The findings presented here will inform the DETAS project's ongoing efforts to strengthen Erasmusintern.org's functionality and broader strategic initiatives. At the same time, they offer actionable insights for policymakers, institutions, and stakeholders seeking to navigate the challenges and opportunities of supporting trainees in an increasingly interconnected and digital world. By situating Erasmusintern.org within this wider context, we will underscore its role as a key tool integrated in a larger ecosystem, while also recognising the scope for innovation and collaboration that lies ahead.

3.2. Erasmusintern.org insights

The Erasmusintern.org platform, designed to bridge the gap between aspiring international trainees and recruiters, has been operational since 2014. The following report offers a synthesis of the platform's data spanning a decade, focusing on user demographics, application trends, recruiter engagement, and the types of opportunities offered. The data analysed spans a period going from 19-08-2014 to 12-09-2024.

3.2.1. User demographics and engagement

Gender distribution

The platform has attracted a total of 187,068 registered users, with women comprising a majority at 58.1% compared to 41.9% men. This proportion holds steady across new users in the last 12 months, where 59.4% of sign-ups were women. This gender balance reflects the broad appeal of the platform while highlighting women's active pursuit of international mobility opportunities.

Figure 1. DETAS survey - gender distribution

Enrolment and educational status

Over half of the users (55.4%) were actively enrolled in a degree at the time of registration, while 13.9% were recent graduates (within six months). However, 16.6% of users did not provide educational data, indicating potential gaps in user profiles. This distribution confirms that the platform's primary user base is comprised of students and recent graduates, aligning with Erasmus+ mobility objectives.

Figure 2. DETAS survey - enrolment distribution

Age dynamics

The average age of users upon registration is 23.9 years, with women averaging 23.5 years and men slightly older at 24.5 years. Most users fall within the 21-25 age range, reflecting a demographic aligned with early career and academic transition stages. This consistency in age profile highlights the platform's role in supporting young professionals seeking their first international experience.

Figure 3. DETAS survey - age distribution by gender

Nationality and residence

Users come from 228 nationalities and report residing in 230 countries, showcasing the platform's global reach. Turkey, Italy, and Spain emerge as leading contributors, while users also actively participate from outside Erasmus+ Programme countries, notably in Partner regions. Notably, 14.2% of users from Partner countries live in Programme countries, underscoring cross-regional engagement. At the same time, 5.72%, reported to live abroad at time of sign up, where both the nationality and the country of residence was a Programme country.

There are six mobility categories analysed:

- **Programme Home:** Users who live in their country of nationality, and that country is part of the Erasmus+ Programme.
- **Programme in Programme:** Users who live abroad, but both their nationality and their current country of residence are Erasmus+ Programme countries.
- **Partner in Programme:** Users whose nationality is from a Partner country but currently reside in a Programme country.
- **Programme in Partner:** Users whose nationality is from a Programme country but currently reside in a Partner country.
- **Partner Home:** Users who live in their country of nationality, and that country is a Partner country.
- **Partner in Partner:** Users who live abroad, and both their nationality and their current country of residence are Partner countries.

Among these six categories, the majority (55.6%) reside in their Programme home country. A significant 19.6% live in their Partner home country. The demographic patterns

suggest that Erasmusintern.org effectively supports users across diverse geographic and cultural contexts.

Figure 4. DETAS survey - distribution of user nationalities

3.2.2. Application trends and platform behaviour

Application patterns

Since the platform's inception, 42.4% of users have submitted at least one application, with similar engagement levels among recent users (42.2% in the last 365 days of the period of analysis). Time-to-application data reveals that over half (53.6%) of applicants submit their first application within a day of registration, indicating that users find the platform intuitive and easy to navigate. However, 6% of users take over a year to apply, underscoring a subset of users which may require additional support or incentives to engage fully.

Figure 5. DETAS survey - days between account creation and first application

User retention

On average, users interact with the platform for 162 days, though those who submit applications remain active significantly longer (241 days) compared to non-applicants (104 days). This indicated the platform's ability to maintain user engagement, particularly among active participants, but also reveal opportunities to better retain non-applicants.

Figure 6. DETAS survey - days since account creation and last login

Applications per user

The average number of applications per user is 6.2, with significant variation across demographic criteria such as time of the year, nationality, programme status and gender. The distribution of the number of applications per user is plotted graphically below. Users with more than 50 applications were discarded as irrelevant data.

Figure 7. DETAS survey - applications per person

3.2.3. Recruiter participation and opportunities

Recruiter engagement

The ErasmusIntern platform has seen a robust engagement from recruiters, with a total of 9,920 unique recruiter accounts created since its inception. These recruiters have contributed to over 111,000 traineeship postings, showcasing the platform's significant role in connecting aspiring trainees with diverse international opportunities.

However, the journey has not been without challenges. Among the accounts registered, 8,725 duplicate accounts were identified over the years, created primarily to circumvent posting limits. This issue is symptomatic of a broader challenge in managing scam behaviour on an open-access platform catering to a global audience. While the number of duplicates might seem large, it is important to contextualise it: the duplicates represent attempts by only 1,042 individual recruiters, suggesting a concentrated issue rather than a widespread problem. These duplicate accounts were also created with the aim of bypassing the cap to the posting limit which was introduced to increase the quality of each offer and lead companies to correctly start and close each application process and related posting.

To safeguard the platform's integrity and improve user experience, significant measures have been implemented in recent years:

- A cap was introduced in 2023, limiting recruiters to three visible postings at a time. This has effectively curbed mass posting abuses while maintaining fair access for genuine recruiters.
- Manual review processes have been enhanced, allowing the platform team to detect and remove scam postings swiftly. The platform team actively monitors postings to ensure that fraudulent content is hidden from users, mitigating the risks of exposure to compromised listings.
- Collaborative partnerships have been strengthened to educate recruiters about best practices and compliance with platform policies.

Despite these efforts, scam or misleading postings need to be further curbed and completely eliminated with more efficient, scalable detection systems, as manual monitoring can be resource-intensive and limited in scope.

Looking ahead, the platform team is committed to further enhancing security and quality control. **Planned improvements include:**

- **Automated screening:** Leveraging machine learning tools to identify patterns indicative of scams, allowing for faster and more reliable detection.
- **Programme Home:** Users who live in their country of nationality, and that country is part of the Erasmus+ Programme.
- **Verification processes:** Introducing stricter onboarding requirements for recruiters, such as mandatory identity verification and proof of business legitimacy.
- **Feedback loops:** Empowering users to report suspicious postings and accounts, creating a more community-driven approach to quality assurance.
- **Improved analytics:** Using enhanced data tracking to identify unusual recruiter behaviour proactively.

Figure 8. DETAS survey - company signups

Geographic and field distribution

Internships are offered in 127 countries, with Spain, Greece, and Italy leading in opportunities. Business studies dominate the fields of study mentioned in postings (57%) followed by communication (53.8%), engineering (17.5%) and social sciences (13%). This distribution aligns well with user demand, although there is room to expand fields like natural sciences and agriculture, which currently represent a small share (2.% and 1.% respectively).

Compensation insights

Financial compensation is offered in 35.9% of postings, while 48% do not indicate any form of payment. Other benefits, such as accommodation and transportation, are available in less than 10% of opportunities. These findings reflect a critical area for improvement, as enhancing financial and logistical support could significantly improve the attractiveness of internships.

All-Time Data:

- Financial compensation: 35.93%
- No financial compensation: 48.01%
- Accommodation: 8.81%
- Health Insurance: 1.59%
- Lunch vouchers: 5.98%
- Other: 20.52%
- Reimbursement costs: 1.72%
- Salary: 11.21%
- Transportation costs: 5.11%

Recent Data (last year based on the period of analysis):

- Financial compensation: 41.65%
- No financial compensation: 55.66%
- Accommodation: 10.22%
- Health Insurance: 1.84%
- Lunch vouchers: 6.93%
- Other: 23.80%
- Reimbursement costs: 1.99%
- Salary: 13.01%
- Transportation costs: 5.92%

The ErasmusIntern platform has, over a decade of operation, proven to be an essential connector between aspiring international trainees and recruiters worldwide. Its robust data and performance analysis reveal both strengths and areas of opportunity, setting the stage for its next evolution. Designed initially to focus on its core function—matching high-quality traineeships with engaged candidates—it has already demonstrated its capacity to support thousands of users across diverse demographic and geographic boundaries.

3.2.4. A vision for enhanced engagement

The platform's current scope provides a vital foundation: enabling recruiters and trainees to meet, post offers, and initiate hiring processes. However, its limitations - particularly its inability to track the full lifecycle of a traineeship beyond the hiring phase - present both a challenge and an opportunity. The decision to narrow its focus during its early years was deliberate, ensuring that the platform excelled in its foundational mission before taking on greater complexity. This approach has succeeded in building trust and usability.

Looking forward, the platform team is committed to addressing these limitations and delivering on the untapped potential of Erasmusintern.org. The goal is not merely to match candidates and companies but to transform the entire traineeship journey into a seamless, supportive, and enriching experience for all stakeholders.

Planned innovations to elevate impact

Future improvements aim to make Erasmusintern.org a comprehensive ecosystem for the entire traineeship process. Among the innovations planned within the project DETAS:

1. Tracking the full traineeship journey

Moving beyond the interview and hiring stage, the platform will enable users to track, evaluate, and close the traineeship loop. Tools will include structured feedback systems, mentorship tracking, and automated reminders to ensure active engagements are concluded with quality outcomes. This will maximise the learning potential for trainees while creating accountability for recruiters.

2. Competence and career integration

The introduction of a digital competence compass linked to Europass CV and platforms like LinkedIn will empower trainees to better understand and showcase their skills. This step aligns with broader Erasmus+ goals of fostering employability and career readiness.

3. Enhanced recruiter mechanisms

To ensure quality opportunities, innovations will include improved recruiter onboarding, mentorship evaluation tools, and adherence to sustainable development goals (SDGs). Enhanced verification mechanisms will strengthen trust, while automated fraud detection will further reduce scams, relieving manual workload.

4. Virtual support and accessibility

A virtual agent will guide users through the Erasmus+ process, ensuring access to the right information at the right time. Combined with user-tested improvements to the platform's UX/UI, these features will improve navigation and accessibility, particularly for users with limited digital experience.

5. Quality labels and feedback mechanisms

The introduction of quality labels for hosting organisations based on a strong policy foundation will add transparency to traineeship conditions, bolstered by real-time feedback loops from trainees. This system will help companies improve and ensure trainees feel supported.

The Erasmusintern.org platform is at a pivotal juncture. Its decade-long track record underscores its value, yet the evolving needs of its users demand innovative, strategic adaptations. By extending its reach into the full traineeship lifecycle, introducing advanced analytics and automation, and fostering a culture of accountability and transparency, the platform will redefine international mobility support.

This evolution is not merely about adding features; it is about embracing a vision where every trainee and recruiter interaction is meaningful, equitable, and where Erasmusintern.org transforms from a trusted matchmaking tool into a holistic enabler of international opportunities that continues to uphold the principles of the Erasmus+ programme while pushing its boundaries toward improved international traineeships in the EU.

3.3. Focus group findings

The focus groups conducted as part of the DETAS (Digitalising Erasmus Traineeship Application & Support) project were a pivotal step in understanding the lived experiences of Erasmus+ trainees. These sessions aimed to provide qualitative insights into the challenges, successes, and opportunities for improvement within the Erasmus traineeship ecosystem. By capturing the voices of former trainees from diverse backgrounds and disciplines, the focus groups offered a nuanced perspective on how the Erasmusintern.org platform and related support structures can be enhanced.

Each focus group was carefully designed to explore the traineeship journey through three critical stages: pre-departure preparation, onsite experience, and post-traineeship follow-up. These stages reflect the natural trajectory of a traineeship and encapsulate the touchpoints where support mechanisms are most needed.

As such, these focus groups provide valuable qualitative data. Their insights not only illustrate the strengths of the current Erasmus+ traineeship model but also highlight actionable areas for innovation, ensuring the Erasmus Intern platform can better bridge the gap between students and their professional aspirations effectively.

3.3.1. Methodology

The five focus groups were conducted within the frame of the DETAS project by a range of organising institutions, namely: the Erasmus Student Network (ESN) and the partner universities being the University of Limerick (UL), the University of Latvia (ULV), and West University of Timișoara (UVT). These sessions aimed to capture diverse perspectives from past Erasmus+ trainees, combining qualitative insights with practical recommendations for improving the ErasmusIntern.org platform.

A total of 35 participants - 29 females and 6 males - engaged across multiple focus group sessions, representing a broad geographic scope. Participants hailed from various European countries, including Ireland, Latvia, Romania, Croatia, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Poland, Portugal, with additional small representation from Turkey and Botswana. The group also included participants at different academic levels, such as undergraduate, master's, and PhD candidates, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of experiences across varying educational contexts.

The methodology employed a combination of virtual and in-person formats to maximise accessibility and participation. Tools such as the digital whiteboards were utilised to facilitate interactive discussions, while supplementary chat functions allowed participants to provide additional input. Sessions were structured around three key phases of the Erasmus+ traineeship journey - pre-departure, onsite, and post-traineeship - to ensure a holistic exploration of the traineeship lifecycle.

An innovative role-playing approach centred around role-playing methodologies was introduced to contextualise scenarios and encourage participants to share realistic insights. This creative method, coupled with scenario-based discussions, enabled the focus groups to delve into the specific challenges and opportunities trainees faced at each stage of their mobility experience.

The logistical and methodological rigour of these sessions ensured that the findings were both representative and actionable, forming a solid foundation for the recommendations to improve Erasmusintern.org and the wider Erasmus+ traineeship experience.

3.3.2. Key insights on the pre-departure, onsite, and post-traineeship phases

The focus groups provided detailed insights into the three critical phases of Erasmus+ traineeships: pre-departure, on-site, and post-traineeship. Each phase highlighted specific challenges and opportunities for improvement, forming the basis for targeted recommendations.

Across all phases, participants stressed the importance of consistent communication, clear processes, and better integration of trainees into their host and home institutions. While there were success stories, the experiences of trainees highlighted significant areas for improvement, particularly in pre-departure preparation, workplace support, and the recognition of achievements post-placement. The findings point to a strong potential for strengthening the Erasmus+ traineeship programme, making it more comprehensive and supportive at every stage.

Pre-departure phase

The pre-departure phase emerged as one of the most challenging stages for trainees. Many participants described this period as stressful, citing gaps in information, logistical difficulties, and emotional strain.

Key concerns included the lack of consistent guidance from home institutions. Some universities provided clear support on documentation, funding, and visa processes, while others offered little direction, leaving trainees to navigate complex requirements alone. This inconsistency in support highlighted the need for standardised pre-departure resources and clear step-by-step guidance.

Administrative hurdles, such as delays in grant approvals and difficulties with Learning Agreements, further added to the complexity. Many trainees also faced significant anxiety about practical matters, particularly finding affordable accommodation and preparing for life in a new country. Emotional preparedness was another common theme, with participants recommending peer connections with alumni or former trainees as a way to alleviate fears and provide practical advice.

However, where targeted preparation sessions were provided - covering CV writing, interviews, and self-assessment - participants found them immensely helpful, underscoring their value in building confidence and clarity before departure.

I had to find out everything by myself...my international office had zero experience with traineeships.

On-Site Phase

The on-site phase brought a mix of successes and struggles, heavily influenced by the level of support available from host organisations and the broader environment.

Workplace integration was a recurring theme, with trainees reporting widely varying experiences. Some participants described structured induction programmes that included introductions to colleagues, training, and regular feedback sessions, which facilitated a smooth transition into their roles. Others faced minimal guidance, which left them feeling isolated and unsure of expectations.

I felt very anxious about finding accommodation and if I was going to make any friends...I almost got scammed and it made me very nervous.

Social and cultural support also played a critical role in trainees' experiences. While the Erasmus Student Network (ESN) helped some trainees connect with others and navigate local life, many felt that ESN activities were not always accessible due to timing or work commitments. More inclusive scheduling and dedicated liaisons were suggested as ways to improve this aspect.

Unluckily, I only met my small project team properly. For all others, I wasn't introduced that much. It was hard to get contacts there.

Accommodation continued to be a significant challenge. Trainees frequently struggled with high costs, short-term leases, and limited support in finding reliable housing. Local guidance on affordable options and practical transportation advice were highlighted as essential improvements. Language barriers further complicated daily life in some countries. Participants recommended better access to language resources to help with integration into local communities and workplaces.

Emotional and mental support is needed because sometimes you feel lonely and isolated. However, I am grateful for the Erasmus Student Network (ESN) community.

Post-Traineeship Phase

The post-traineeship phase often lacked sufficient support, with many participants feeling unprepared for the transition back to their home institutions or into the job market.

Career development opportunities varied. While some trainees secured roles directly linked to their placements, others found it difficult to articulate their skills and experiences to potential employers. Structured feedback from supervisors and access to professional recommendations were seen as critical in addressing this gap. Recognition of traineeship achievements within academic frameworks was inconsistent. Participants often encountered difficulties in ensuring their credits were properly integrated into their academic records. This process requires clearer communication and streamlined procedures across institutions.

Emotional adjustment upon returning home was another recurring issue. Many trainees described feelings of disconnection and reverse culture shock, suggesting that alumni networks or peer support groups could provide much-needed continuity and connection during this phase.

Make traineeships as popular and well-known as exchange programs, and have a good network from the beginning.

3.3.3. Platform-specific feedback

Participants across all focus groups offered valuable feedback on the Erasmusintern.org platform, highlighting its strengths and areas for improvement. While the platform serves as a vital link between trainees and organisations, users identified specific challenges and proposed enhancements to optimise its usability and relevance for diverse stakeholders.

Awareness and usability

A recurring theme was the need to upscale the awareness about Erasmusintern.org, with only a minority of participants indicating prior knowledge of the platform before their traineeship. Some participants discovered it through informal channels rather than institutional promotion. This points to a need for increased outreach, potentially through university partnerships, targeted campaigns, and student networks like ESN.

On usability, participants noted the platform's potential as a centralised hub but identified gaps in its functionality. For instance, one participant observed that traineeship descriptions can lack key details about host organisations, such as company size, structure, or specific tasks. The need for such information left some users uncertain about their placements until they arrived on-site.

Pre-departure resources

Several participants emphasised the importance of clear, structured guidance on the application process. They recommended adding step-by-step guides, including timelines for documentation submission, visa procedures, and learning agreement preparation. A common suggestion was the creation of a searchable database of past trainees' feedback and contact details, allowing users to connect with alumni for advice on specific organisations or locations.

The participants also suggested adding in the platform services related to accommodation support. Participants proposed integrating accommodation resources directly into the platform, with features like verified housing listings and country-specific legal advice on renting. This would alleviate a major source of stress during the pre-departure phase.

Enhancing search and matching features

Many participants found the search functionality needing improvement, particularly for filtering traineeships that align with specific academic or professional needs. PhD candidates highlighted the lack of opportunities tailored to their level, suggesting the introduction of a dedicated section for research-based traineeships. Additionally, participants proposed keyword-based notifications to inform users of new postings matching their interests, enhancing engagement and timely applications.

Integration with support networks

The lack of connection to local Erasmus Student Network (ESN) chapters was a missed opportunity noted by participants. They suggested that Erasmusintern.org could provide information about ESN sections in host cities, facilitating access to cultural, social, and logistical support. For areas without active ESN chapters, participants recommended host organisations designate mentors to assist with local integration and guidance.

Transparency and quality assurance

Participants called for greater transparency and quality assurance in the platform's listings. Concerns were shared over traineeships without financial compensation. While recognising the voluntary nature of some roles, participants advocated for clearer indicators of benefits provided, such as accommodation or travel reimbursement. This would allow trainees to make informed decisions and set realistic expectations.

Another suggestion was to incorporate a feedback and rating system for host organisations, enabling users to evaluate their experiences and provide insights for future trainees. This aligns with ongoing efforts under the DETAS project to introduce quality labels for companies and improve reporting mechanisms.

Scalability and future enhancements

Participants appreciated the platform's role in facilitating cross-border traineeships but highlighted the need for features that extend beyond the recruitment phase. Suggestions included tracking the traineeship lifecycle, from onboarding to post-internship evaluation. This would not only improve the platform's utility but also provide valuable data for continuous improvement.

3.4. Survey results

3.4.1. Respondent demographics

The survey captured feedback from 4,013 valid respondents, representing diverse academic and geographical backgrounds. Women comprised the majority at 60%, while men represented 39%, and 1% identified as non-binary. Regarding education, bachelor's degree students dominated the survey with 48% of responses, followed closely by master's students at 46%. PhD candidates and "other" educational categories constituted a smaller proportion, each contributing approximately 3%.

Language proficiency was a critical factor for traineeships, with 45% of respondents rating their English skills at C1 (advanced) and 16% at C2 (mastery). Intermediate levels (B1 and B2) accounted for 37%, while only 2% identified as elementary or beginner.

3.4.2. Pre-departure insights

Respondents primarily discovered Erasmus+ traineeships through their universities (46%) and the ErasmusIntern.org portal (25%). A smaller percentage cited friends, social media, or company websites. While nearly half of respondents (43%) secured a traineeship within 1-3 months, others required more time, with 16% taking 3-6 months and 17% over six months.

Most respondents (81%) found the application process clear and straightforward, with the ErasmusIntern portal emerging as the most helpful resource (41%). However, university career services (31%) and peer advice (13%) also played significant roles.

Regarding pre-departure support, 45% of respondents reported receiving training or orientation from their sending institutions. Suggestions for improvement highlighted the need for better financial guidance (49%), networking opportunities with past trainees (45%), and more thorough orientation sessions (32%).

3.4.3. On-site experience

The overall traineeship experience received positive feedback, with 78% of respondents rating their time as "good" or "excellent" (weighted average: 4.13/5). Host organisations were commended for supporting integration into the local environment, with an average

satisfaction score of 4/5. However, cultural and language barriers remained a challenge for 38% of participants.

Mentorship and guidance were generally well-rated, achieving a score of 3.96/5. Respondents found their assigned tasks largely relevant to their academic and career goals, with 70% scoring this aspect a 4 or 5 out of 5.

Challenges faced during the traineeships included managing financial expenses (49%), adapting to local culture or language (27%), and a lack of guidance from host organisations (19%).

3.4.4. Post-traineeship reflections

The impact of Erasmus+ traineeships on career prospects was notable, with 76% of respondents reporting moderate to significant benefits. Despite this, only 31% of participants received job offers or continued opportunities from their host organisations. The likelihood of recommending Erasmus+ traineeships to peers was high, with 87% expressing strong support.

Recognition of traineeships by sending institutions was reported by 61% of respondents, though 22% stated that their experiences were only partially recognised.

3.4.5. Feedback on the Erasmusintern.org portal

The portal was rated positively for its user-friendliness, with a weighted average score of 3.98/5. Most respondents (84%) found the information they needed easily accessible. The search and application feature was identified as the most useful, while the internship rating and review system and support FAQs were less impactful.

Respondents suggested enhancements such as integrating trainee profiles with a competence compass, adding a virtual agent for guidance, and improving accessibility and user experience. Tracking the continuous traineeship journey and implementing quality labels for host organisations were also highlighted as priorities for improvement.

3.5. Conclusion: bridging mobility and digital innovation

In Part III we highlighted the pivotal role of ErasmusIntern.org as a transformative digital platform in the Erasmus+ traineeship ecosystem. Through an in-depth analysis of platform data, user surveys, and focus group discussions, this section underscores the achievements of the platform while also revealing areas for growth and improvement.

The findings affirm that ErasmusIntern.org is more than a matchmaking tool - it is an enabler of international mobility, fostering connections between trainees and recruiters across diverse geographies and disciplines. Its ability to support users throughout the application process, coupled with its reach across a wide demographic spectrum, establishes it as a cornerstone tool supporting the Erasmus+ programme.

However, the analysis also identifies critical gaps in the platform's functionality, particularly its limited engagement with the full traineeship lifecycle. The absence of tools to track and support trainees during and after their placements represents a missed opportunity to enhance user experiences, strengthen outcomes, and drive quality improvements.

Focus group discussions and survey insights further highlight recurring challenges, such as inconsistent pre-departure preparation, varying levels of on-site support, and insufficient post-traineeship recognition. These issues reflect broader systemic gaps in the mobility experience, which the platform has the potential to address through targeted innovations.

Looking ahead, ErasmusIntern.org must evolve into a more holistic ecosystem that not only connects trainees and recruiters but also supports the entire mobility journey. Planned enhancements, including the integration of tracking tools, mentorship evaluation mechanisms, and quality assurance labels, offer promising avenues for addressing existing shortcomings. These improvements align with the DETAS project's broader goals of digitalising and enhancing the Erasmus+ traineeship experience.

Charts and tables

1. Figure 1. DETAS survey - gender distribution
2. Figure 2. DETAS survey - enrolment distribution
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